

PEDAGOGICAL POSSIBILITIES OF POPULARIZING NATIONAL MUSICAL CULTURE AMONG YOUTH

Akhmedova Inobat Bakhodirovna

Urgench State University

Teacher of the department "Music Education"

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14547388>

Abstract: This article studies the pedagogical possibilities of popularizing national musical culture among young people. The importance of music education in promoting national culture, its educational and aesthetic possibilities are highlighted. The educational power of music in forming the aesthetic taste of young people through national music, strengthening their sense of patriotism, and developing them as individuals is analyzed. The article presents practical recommendations on the effectiveness of using interactive and innovative methods in working with pupils and students, and on the use of national musical instruments in the classroom. The role and possibilities of modern technologies in attracting young people to national musical culture are also considered.

Keywords: National musical culture, youth education, pedagogical possibilities, aesthetic taste, patriotism, innovative methods, music education, national instruments, modern technologies.

Introduction.

National music is the heart, history and soul of the people. The Uzbek national musical culture has been formed over centuries and embodies the hopes, sorrows and joys of our ancestors. In today's era of globalization, when different cultures are merging, preserving our national music and passing it on to the younger generation is an urgent task. Popularizing national music among young people not only educates them as individuals with musical taste, but also helps them understand their identity, instill love for their people and the culture of their homeland.

Our national music is not just an art or entertainment sphere, but also contains the rich history, traditions, customs and values of the people. Maqams, songs and epics that express the spirit of the people have unlimited potential to broaden the worldview of our youth and form their positive attitude to life. However, in today's age of technology, it is clear that our national music does not have enough space in the minds of young people.

So, what pedagogical opportunities are there to popularize national music? How can this rich heritage be conveyed to the hearts of modern youth and instill

in them a genuine respect for our national culture? This article seeks answers to these questions. The role of national music in the education of youth, ways of its promotion using modern technologies, and the effectiveness of pedagogical approaches are discussed.

Methodology.

The process of popularizing national musical culture among youth requires well-thought-out pedagogical strategies and innovative approaches. In this study, a number of methodological approaches were used to identify effective methods of teaching and promoting national music. Based on the theoretical and practical principles of pedagogy, the main factors in the process of instilling national music in the minds of young people were studied.

First, the role of modern interactive methods in teaching national music was analyzed. This approach, by encouraging students to actively participate in the lesson process, allows them to form their musical taste and increase their interest in national culture. For example, through practical training in national instruments, listening to songs and performing them, a favorable environment is created for students to deeply understand national values.

Secondly, during the study, the possibilities of information and communication technologies for popularizing national music among young people were studied. Providing national music to a wide audience through digital resources, online platforms and social networks was considered one of the effective ways to popularize it among young people. At the same time, taking into account the age characteristics of students, a strategy was developed to connect their interest in technology with national musical culture.

Third, the study analyzed the importance of various cultural events, seminars and competitions to increase the impact of national music. Attracting young people to national music festivals, including them in musical ensembles, and ensuring their participation in creative projects were noted as important steps in increasing their interest in national culture.

Thus, these methodological approaches can serve as an important practical tool in popularizing national music culture among young people. In this process, the use of an individual approach in working with pupils and students, the combination of national values with modern technologies, and the stimulation of creative activity were identified as the main factors.

Discussion:

Although the issue of popularizing national music culture among young people, at first glance, seems to be a simple process, in fact, it is a complex and

multifaceted pedagogical process. The success of this process depends on the readiness of young people to accept cultural values, the correct approach to them, and the presentation of national music in modern ways.

During the discussion, it was found that relying only on traditional methods is not enough to instill national music in the hearts of young people. Today's youth live in an era of rapid information exchange, and in order to attract their attention, it is necessary to apply modern technologies to the educational process. For example, initiatives such as presenting the performance of national instruments in digital format, creating interactive textbooks or mobile applications of national music can increase interest in music among young people.

It is also important to create a creative environment to form interest in national music among young people. Festivals and competitions, extracurricular clubs, concerts and creative projects are showing their effectiveness in promoting the main values of national music. This not only increases the interest of young people, but also develops their musical taste and creativity.

However, there are also problems in this process. Some young people consider national musical culture to be less interesting than modern musical genres. This requires us to present national music in modern ways, bringing it closer to the everyday lives of young people. For example, integrating national musical motifs into modern pop and electronic music, and promoting them on popular cultural platforms among young people, can be a successful approach in this regard.

In addition, popularizing national musical culture requires close cooperation not only with young people, but also with parents, teachers, and all segments of society. Instilling national values in the process of music education and increasing young people's respect for culture should be not only the task of the teacher, but also the general goal of society.

In conclusion, the popularization of national musical culture among young people should be carried out through a combination of pedagogical approaches and taking into account modern requirements. Making national music an integral part of the cultural, aesthetic and spiritual development of young people is one of the most effective ways to successfully convey our national values to the future generation.

Conclusion.

National musical culture is a vivid expression of the spiritual wealth of the people, an awareness of national identity. Passing on this rich heritage to the

younger generation is an important task not only of the education system, but also of every member of society. The results of the study showed that the use of modern and creative forms of pedagogical approaches in popularizing national music among young people is the key to success.

In today's age of technology, it is important to use interactive tools that match their interests, combine them with modern musical genres, and use digital platforms to attract young people to national music. Also, promoting national music through cultural events, festivals and creative competitions allows young people to make this cultural heritage a part of their lives.

National music not only develops aesthetic taste, but also embodies feelings of patriotism, national pride and devotion to values. The role of national music in shaping the cultural consciousness of our youth is invaluable. However, for this process to be successful, a systematic and collaborative approach is necessary. Teachers, parents and other segments of society must work together to pass on this rich heritage to the next generation.

In short, by instilling national musical culture in the hearts of young people, we not only ensure their cultural and spiritual maturity, but also contribute to the preservation and development of the rich history and values of our people. This process is one of the most effective ways to teach self-awareness and respect for national values. If young people love and learn national music, this heritage will never disappear, but rather will be enriched through new generations.

References:

1. Abdullaev, B. (2015). History of Uzbek national musical culture. Tashkent: Fan.
2. Nazarova, D. (2019). Innovative technologies in musical education. Tashkent: Akademnashr.
3. Qodirov, Sh. (2018). Social significance of musical culture. Samarkand: SamDU edition.
4. Yunusova, Z. Kh. (2010). Shashmakom and its role in the upbringing of youth. Tashkent: Marifat.
5. Nazarbekova, G. (2020). Development of the creative potential of preschool children in national musical art. Tashkent: Manaviyat.
6. UNESCO (2003). Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage. Retrieved from <https://ich.unesco.org>
7. Nettle, B. (1983). The Study of Ethnomusicology: Thirty-one Issues and Concepts. Urbana: University of Illinois Press.
8. Rice, T. (2014). Ethnomusicology: A Very Short Introduction. Oxford: Oxford University Press.